

EXPLORING LEARNING THROUGH SIMULATION TOWARDS THE ENHANCEMENT OF LIFE SKILLS OF THE 2ND YEAR (BTTE-LDP) 2018-2019 PRE-SERVICE TEACHER AT TUP-TAGUIG

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to know how far the effectiveness of learning through simulations to their life skills of the BTTE students. This study will help the students to determine their learning through simulation in enhancing their life skills for the improvement of the ability of the students. The method used in this research is quantitative data with correlational analysis. The techniques used to collect the data is survey questionnaire. Whereas the sample used are the students of 2nd year (BTTE-LDP) 2018-2019 at the Technological University of the Philippines Taguig. The researcher develops 5 items for each variable to identify the ability of the students in terms of life skill through learning simulations. Based on the results, most of the respondents are 22 years old, male and came from Automotive Engineering Technology. It is also found out that most of the student had strongly agree that learning through simulation in terms of active engagement, transfer of knowledge, deliberate practice and self-reflection will help them to improve their performance. Furthermore, the correlation between the respondents to their Life Skills through learning simulation has a weak relationship. The significant of learning through simulation has no relationship with their life skills in terms of critical thinking, self-awareness, decision-making and problem solving.

Keywords: *Life Skills, Pre-Service Teachers, Learning through Simulation, Bachelor of Technical Teacher (BTTE), Ladderized Degree Program (LDP)*

INTRODUCTION

In the fast-facing transition of the world and the modernization of the social life of the people, the students used to do are not enough anymore. Real world is a real world

is it not? With the growth of industrialization and improving efficiency in technology, industries by far, have used electronics intensively for its advantage over. In the perspective of and observation of the researchers, the transferring of knowledge and teaching process might not be enough if the teachers focus only on the discussion, for it because the 21st century students are now globally competitive and hungrier to achieve a successful life. As such, the researchers had come up with this study because as the researchers observe, the students are on discussion they are easily distracted in simple noise, commotions and most especially on their gadgets. One of the hindrances that the students may also encounter when they focus on the discussion is that they cannot use their learning through discussion in real life.

The goal of this study is to enhance the life skills of pre-service teachers in terms of decision-making, problem solving, critical thinking and self-awareness in learning through simulation in their area of specialization for them to be prepared in their professional career.

Research Questions

As pre-service teacher we must know how adapt with the demand and change in our society to motivate and bring academic excellence to the student and continually know how to enhance theoretical understanding and life skills through practical exposure and simulation. The study specifically needs to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex; and,
 - 1.3 Area of specialization?
2. How do the BTTE students describe their learning through simulation in terms of:
 - 2.1 Active Engagement;
 - 2.2 Transfer of Knowledge;
 - 2.3 Deliberate Practice; and,
 - 2.4 Self-reflection?
3. How can learning through simulation enhance the life skill of BTTE students in terms of:
 - 3.1 Critical Thinking;
 - 3.2 Self-awareness;
 - 3.3 Decision-making; and,
 - 3.4 Problem Solving?
4. Does the profile of the respondents have significant relationship in enhancing the life skills of BTTE students?
5. Does learning through simulation have a significant relationship in enhancing the life skills of the BTTE students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research method used in this study is descriptive correlational method. This method research is generally constructivism perception which leads to explore learning through simulation towards the enhancements of the life skills of Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education students at Technological University of the Philippines-Taguig

The researchers used survey questionnaire to analyze the input of learning through simulation towards the enhancement of the BTTE students. All data collected should lead to better understanding of this study.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted at the Basic Arts and Science Department at the Technological University of the Philippines-Taguig. Located at 14Km East Service Road Western Bicutan Taguig City.

Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were the 2nd year Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education at the Basic Applied Science Department at the Technological University of the Philippines-Taguig with different specialization such as Electronics Engineering Technology (ELEX), Non-Destructive Engineering Technology (NDT), Chemical Engineering Technology (CHET), Automotive Engineering Technology(AET), Electrical Engineering Technology(EET), Tool and Die Engineering Technology (TDT), Electro-mechanical Engineering Technology(EMET) and Architecture Engineering Technology (ARKI).

Research Instrument

The researcher used survey questionnaire as the main tool for gathering the information needed in the study. The researcher found it as a tool which is easier to use. It is also lessened the time consumed, less expensive and easier to interpret and analyze. This study is comprising of three parts: Part 1: the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex and area of specialization. Part 2: has the indicator of learning through simulation such as active engagement, deliberate practice, transfer of knowledge and self-reflection. Part 3: has the indicators of life skills in terms of critical thinking, self-awareness, decision-making and problem solving.

Validation of Questionnaire

To make sure that the questionnaire is valid and reliable, the draft of the questionnaire was submitted to the thesis adviser to address some comments and recommendation before it was pretested for certain validation among the respondents of 2nd year BTTE students. The research acquired Cronbach-Alpha result of (0.9457) of the

questionnaires administered for validation. It denotes that the questionnaire is valid and reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the refinement of the instrument, the researchers prepared the entire survey questionnaire to be distributed and to be answered by the respondents. The researchers also administered the survey sheets to the randomly respondents. After questionnaire were gathered, the data was checked, tabulated, and analyzed in through the use of the statistical tests best fitted to measure the indicators used for this study.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

These are the following statistical tools that were used for the data analysis in order to endure reliable and valid interpretation.

1. The frequency and percentage counts were utilized to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and area of specialization.
2. Weighted mean and Standard Deviation to determine the perception on the learning through simulation and for the life skills of the BTTE students.

Interpreting the Weighted Mean

Mean Range	Verbal Description
4.51 - 5.00	Strongly Agree
3.51 - 4.50	Agree
2.51 - 3.50	Neither Agree nor Disagree
1.51 - 2.50	Disagree
1.00 - 1.50	Strongly Disagree

3. Correlation analysis, to determine the significant relationship of the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and area of specialization towards the life skills of the BTTE students.
4. Multiple Regression, to determine if the learning through simulation significantly enhances the life skills of the BTTE students.

Interpreting the Strength of *R* (Correlation Coefficient)

Scale	Descriptive Interpretation
0.03 to 0.30 or -0.01 to -0.30	Weak Relationship
0.31 to 0.60 or -0.31 to -0.60	Moderate Relationship
0.61 to 1.00 or -0.61 to -1.00	Strong Relationship

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the respondents was considered in this study as to age, sex and area of specialization.

Age of the Respondents

In this study, the age refers to the chronological age or the time that the respondents existed. It is also the quality of the mind and is equated with wisdom and experience. The ages of the respondents are presented in the figure below.

Figure 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondent's Age

Figure 1 indicates that most of the respondents are age 22. The figure shows that the majority of the respondents are the age of 21-24 which most of them are 22 years old with a frequency of 12(48%); 10 (38%) are from 25-28 years old; 2 (8%) are from 29-32 years old and 2 (8%) are from 33 – 36 years old.

Area of Specialization

Figure 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondent's Area of Specialization

This illustrates that most of the respondents are Automotive Engineering Technology (AET). Figure 2 shows that the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of area of specialization. Four (4) of the respondents which is equivalent to fifteen percent (15%) are Electronics Engineering Technology (ELEX) students. Two (2) of the respondents which is equivalent to eight percent (8%) are Non-Destructive Engineering Technology (NDT) students. Four (4) of the respondents which is equivalent to fifteen percent (15%) are Chemical Engineering Technology (CHET) students. Ten (10) of the respondents which is equivalent to thirty-eight percent (38%) are Automotive Engineering Technology (AET) students. One (1) of the respondents which is equivalent to four percent (4%) are Electrical Engineering Technology (EET) students. One (1) of the respondents which is equivalent to four percent (4%) are Tool and Die Engineering Technology (TDET) students. Three (3) of the respondents which is equivalent to twelve percent (12%) are Electro-Mechanical Engineering Technology

(EMET). One (1) of the respondents which is equivalent to four percent (4%) are Architectural Engineering Technology (ARKI) students.

Sex of the Respondents

In this research, sex refers to the biological and physical differences between men and women. Men and women are born with similar capabilities but differ in with regards to their role. The sex of the respondents is shown below.

Figure 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondent's Sex

Figure 3 indicates that most of the respondents are MALE. Figure shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of sex. Eighteen (18) of the respondents which is equivalent to sixty-nine percent (69%) are Male and Eight (8) of the respondents which is equivalent to thirty-one percent (31%) are females.

Learning through Simulation

In learning through simulations, students get the chance to apply their learning toward solving a problem similar to one they might encounter in real life, but without the inherent risks.

Active Engagement

Active engagement refers to the actively engagement of the respondent's activities that encourage them to develop deeper understanding of content by working.

Table 1. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation in terms of Active Engagement

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I engaged myself on hands-on activities	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
I am interested in learning activities	4.65	0.48	Strongly Agree
I am an active learner	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
I am encouraged to think actively and creatively	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
I explore on my own	4.73	0.44	Strongly Agree
Total	4.60	0.48	Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows that the learning through simulation indicated by active learning, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Strongly Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.48$) as described by the respondents.

Additionally, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they are engaged themselves on hands on activities ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$); interested in learning activities ($\bar{X} = 4.65$, $SD = 0.48$); they are active learner ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$); encouraged to think actively and creatively ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$); and explore things on their own ($\bar{X} = 4.73$, $SD = 0.44$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This implies that the respondents who are actively engaged on hands activities, interested in learning activity, active learner, encouraged to think actively and creatively and explore on their own.

Transfer of Knowledge

Transfer of knowledge is a well-done simulation to a new problem or new set of parameters that require the respondents to extend their earlier learning.

Table 2. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation in terms of Transfer of Knowledge

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I apply my new knowledge to create new product	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
I share my prior knowledge in the activities that benefit others	4.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
I discuss my output activities in front of other people.	4.69	0.46	Strongly Agree
I make a project that can be used by the others	4.46	0.50	Agree
I distribute knowledge and ensure its availability in the future	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
Total	4.57	0.49	Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the learning through simulation indicated by transfer of knowledge, as reflected, all indicators illustrated as Strongly Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.57$, $SD = 0.49$) as described by the respondents.

Furthermore, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they apply their new knowledge to create new product ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$); share my prior knowledge in the activities that benefit others ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.49$); discuss my output activities in front of other people ($\bar{X} = 4.69$, $SD = 0.46$); make a project that can be used by the others and distribute knowledge ($\bar{X} = 4.46$, $SD = 0.50$) and ensure its availability in the future ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This signifies that the respondents can apply their new knowledge to create new product, share my prior knowledge in the activities that benefit others, discuss my output activities in front of other people, make a project that can be used by the others and distribute knowledge and ensure its availability in the future.

Deliberate Practice

Deliberate practice is a concept popularized by psychologist Anders Ericsson and refers to a methodical and focused approach to improving skills or performance in a particular area. It involves engaging in activities that are specifically designed to enhance one's abilities, with the aim of achieving mastery or excellence in that area.

Table 3. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation in terms of Deliberate Practice

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I perform activities to increase my learning	4.73	0.44	Strongly Agree
I exert effort to improve my performance on hands-on activities	4.73	0.44	Strongly Agree
I appreciate informative feedback that helps improve my output activities	4.77	0.42	Strongly Agree
I monitor my performance in doing activity	4.50	0.64	Agree
I am motivated to perform the task.	4.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
Total	4.67	0.49	Strongly Agree

Table 3 reveals the learning through simulation indicated by deliberate practice, as reflected, all indicators illustrated as Strongly Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.67$, $SD = 0.49$) as described by the respondents.

Additionally, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they perform activities to increase their learning ($\bar{X} = 4.73$, $SD = 0.44$); exert effort to improve performance on hands on activities ($\bar{X} = 4.73$, $SD = 0.44$); appreciate informative feedback that helps improve output activities ($\bar{X} = 4.77$, $SD = 0.42$); monitor performance

in doing the activity ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.64$); and motivated to perform the task ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.49$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This signifies that the respondents who are actively engaged in deliberate practices can perform to increase their learning, exert effort to improve performance on hands on activities, appreciate informative feedback that helps improve output activities, monitor performance in doing the activity and motivated to perform the task.

Self-reflection

Self-reflection is a cognitive process wherein individuals examine their thoughts, feelings, actions, and experiences. It involves introspection and evaluation of one's beliefs, values, goals, and behaviors. Self-reflection is not merely about thinking about oneself but rather about critically analyzing one's thoughts and actions in order to gain insights, improve understanding, and make positive changes.

Table 4. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation in terms of Self-reflection

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I look back on my action after doing a task	4.42	0.49	Agree
I am aware on my learning performance	4.58	0.49	Strongly Agree
I know my strength and weaknesses in doing hands-on activities	4.58	0.63	Strongly Agree
I accept feedback from others to improve my performance	4.65	0.48	Strongly Agree
I do activities on my own	4.96	0.19	Strongly Agree
Total	4.64	0.46	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that the learning through simulation indicated by self-reflection, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Strongly Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.64$, $SD = 0.46$) as described by the respondents.

Moreover, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they look back on their action after doing a task ($\bar{X} = 4.42$, $SD = 0.49$); aware on their learning performance ($\bar{X} = 4.58$, $SD = 0.49$); know their strength and weaknesses in doing hands-on activities ($\bar{X} = 4.58$, $SD = 0.63$); accept feedback from others to improve their performance ($\bar{X} = 4.65$, $SD = 0.48$) and do activities on their own ($\bar{X} = 4.96$, $SD = 0.19$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This implies that the respondents as they look back on their action after doing a task, aware on their learning performance, know their strength

and weaknesses in doing hands-on activities, accept feedback from others to improve their performance and do activities on their own.

Life Skills

Life skills encompass a range of abilities that enable individuals to navigate the complexities of daily life and effectively cope with various challenges. According to Zins, et. Al (2018), life skills are defined as "abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life" (Zins, et.al 2018, p. 1). These skills are not innate but are instead learned and acquired through experience, education, and social interaction.

Critical Thinking

Critical thinking is a multifaceted cognitive process that involves analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating information in order to make informed decisions or form well-reasoned beliefs. At its core, critical thinking is about approaching problems or situations with an open mind and a willingness to question assumptions, consider alternative perspectives, and weigh evidence objectively.

Table 5. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation of their Life Skills in terms of Critical thinking

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I can clearly think while on discussion	4.58	0.49	Strongly Agree
I can understand the links between the ideas	4.54	0.50	Strongly Agree
I can learn by actual activities	4.54	0.57	Strongly Agree
I can analyze lesson orderly	4.38	0.56	Agree
I can assess the information being received	4.46	0.50	Agree
Total	4.50	0.52	Agree

Table 5 shows that the learning through simulation enhance their life skills indicated by critical thinking, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.52$) as described by the respondents.

Moreover, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they can clearly think while on discussion ($\bar{X} = 4.58$, $SD = 0.49$); can understand the links between the idea ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.50$); can learn by actual activities ($\bar{X} = 4.54$, $SD = 0.57$); an analyze lesson orderly ($\bar{X} = 4.38$, $SD = 0.56$); and can assess the information being received ($\bar{X} = 4.46$, $SD = 0.50$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This implies that the respondents as they can clearly think while on discussion, can understand the links between the ideas, can learn by actual activities, an analyze lesson orderly and can assess the information being received.

Self-awareness

Self-awareness is a being conscious of what you are good at while acknowledging what you still have yet to learn. Self-awareness is when people know what they want in their lives, what makes them happy, what they want to change or improve in them and what are their most important belief and values.

Table 6. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation of their Life Skills in terms of Self-awareness

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I can understand my own needs and desires	4.42	0.49	Agree
I can pay attention to my emotion and how I work	4.46	0.50	Agree
I can control my emotion when doing my tasks	4.19	0.62	Agree
I can be conscious of where I am good	4.50	0.69	Agree
I can be open to learn new things.	4.88	0.32	Strongly Agree
Total	4.49	0.53	Agree

Table 6 shows that the learning through simulation enhance their life skills indicated by self-awareness, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.49$, $SD = 0.53$) as described by the respondents.

Additionally, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they can understand their own needs and desires ($\bar{X} = 4.42$, $SD = 0.49$); can pay attention to their emotion and how they work ($\bar{X} = 4.46$, $SD = 0.50$); can control their emotion when doing their tasks ($\bar{X} = 4.19$, $SD = 0.62$); can be conscious of where they are good ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.69$) and can be open to learn new things ($\bar{X} = 4.88$, $SD = 0.32$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This signifies that the respondents can understand their own needs and desires, can pay attention to their emotion and how they work, can control their emotion when doing their tasks, can be conscious of where they are good and can be open to learn new things.

Decision-making

In its simplest sense, decision-making is the act of choosing between two or more courses of action. In the wider process of problem-solving, decision-making involves choosing between possible solutions to a problem.

Table 7. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation of their Life Skills in terms of Decision-making

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I can gather enough data in making decision	4.50	0.64	Agree
I can plan ahead before making decisions	4.65	0.55	Strongly Agree

I can think for the benefits of other when making decision	4.62	0.56	Strongly Agree
I can be responsible in every decision that I make	4.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
I can consider opinions when making decision.	4.35	0.48	Agree
Total	4.55	0.54	Strongly Agree

Table 7 shows that the learning through simulation enhance their life skills indicated by decision-making, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Strongly Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.55$, $SD = 0.54$) as described by the respondents.

Furthermore, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they can gather enough data in making decision ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.64$); can plan ahead before making decision ($\bar{X} = 4.65$, $SD = 0.55$); can think for the benefits of other when making decision ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.56$); can be responsible in every decision that they make ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.49$) and can consider opinions when making decision ($\bar{X} = 4.35$, $SD = 0.48$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This signifies that the respondents can gather enough data in making decision, can plan ahead before making decisions, can think for the benefits of other when making decision, can be responsible in every decision that they make and can consider opinions when making decision.

Problem Solving

Good problem solvers use a combination of intuition and logic to come up with their solutions. Intuition has more to do with the emotional and instinctive side of us and logic is more related to our cognition and thinking.

Table 8. Pre-service Teachers Responses in Learning through Simulation of their Life Skills in terms of Problem Solving

Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I can assess the problem with an open mind	4.31	0.67	Agree
I can deal constructively with the problems that I encounter	4.27	0.71	Strongly Agree
I can breakdown problems to understand easily	4.19	0.79	Agree
I can think through issues logically	4.35	0.68	Agree
I can come up with the best possible solution in a real-world problem	4.19	0.39	Agree
Total	4.26	0.65	Agree

Table 8 shows that the learning through simulation enhance their life skills indicated by problem solving, as reflected, all the indicators illustrated as Agree ($\bar{X} = 4.26$, $SD = 0.65$) as described by the respondents.

Additionally, the table shows that the respondents are strongly agree as they can assess the problem with an open mind ($\bar{X} = 4.31$, $SD = 0.67$); can deal constructively with the problems that they encounter ($\bar{X} = 4.27$, $SD = 0.71$); can breakdown problems to understand easily ($\bar{X} = 4.19$, $SD = 0.79$); can think through issues logically ($\bar{X} = 4.35$, $SD = 0.68$) and can come up with the best possible solution in a real-world problem ($\bar{X} = 4.19$, $SD = 0.39$).

Small values of standard deviation denote that the responses from the respondents are homogenous. This signifies that the respondents can assess the problem with an open mind, can deal constructively with the problems that they encounter, can breakdown problems to understand easily, can think through issues logically and can come up with the best possible solution in a real-world problem.

Correlation Analysis

In research, correlation analysis serves as a valuable tool for examining relationships between variables. However, it's important to note that correlation does not imply causation. As stated by Sullivan (2019), "correlation provides an indication that there is a relationship between two variables; it does not, however, indicate that one variable causes the other" (p. 98). This principle underscores the need for caution when interpreting correlation coefficients.

For instance, suppose we have two variables, A and B, and their correlation coefficient indicates a strong positive relationship. This correlation could be due to various factors. It's plausible that A causes B, meaning changes in A lead to corresponding changes in B. Conversely, it's also possible that B causes A, where variations in B influence the values of A. Moreover, as Sullivan (2019) further highlights, "an additional variable (C) could cause both A and B" (p. 98). This scenario introduces the concept of a third variable, which may confound the relationship between A and B.

Table 9. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Critical Thinking

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.010	0.05	Weak Relationship
Sex	-0.042	0.05	Weak Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.216	0.05	Weak Relationship
Total	0.061	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 9 shows that there is a weak relationship ($r\text{-value} = 0.061$) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of critical thinking. It shows that there is a weak relationship ($r\text{-value} = 0.010$, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their critical thinking skills. It appears that there is a weak relationship ($r\text{-value} = -0.042$, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's sex and their critical thinking skills. It pointed out that male have the weak relationship in terms of critical thinking. In terms of area of

specialization, it displays shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = 0.216, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's area of specialization and their critical thinking skills.

Thus, the overall findings mean that there is a weak relationship of critical thinking of the life skills among the profile of the BTTE students.

Table 10. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Self-awareness

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.014	0.05	Weak Relationship
Sex	0.022	0.05	Weak Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.012	0.05	Weak Relationship
Total	0.016	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 10 shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = 0.016) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of self-awareness. It shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = 0.014, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their self-awareness skills. It appears that there is a weak relationship (r -value = -0.022, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's sex and their self-awareness skills.

Additionally, in terms of area of specialization, it displays shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = -0.012, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's area of specialization and their self-awareness skills.

Thus, the overall findings mean that there is a weak relationship of self-awareness of the life skills among the profile of the BTTE students.

Table 11. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Decision-making

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.041	0.05	Weak Relationship
Sex	0.329	0.05	Moderate Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.339	0.05	Moderate Relationship
Total	0.236	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 12 shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = 0.236) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of decision-making. It shows that there is a weak relationship (r -value = 0.041, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their decision-making skills.

Table 8. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Self-awareness

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.014	0.05	Weak Relationship

Sex	0.022	0.05	Weak Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.012	0.05	Weak Relationship
Total	0.016	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 13 shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.016) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of self-awareness. It shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.014, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their self-awareness skills. It appears that there is a weak relationship (r-value = -0.022, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's sex and their self-awareness skills.

Moreover, in terms of area of specialization, it displays shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = -0.012, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's area of specialization and their self-awareness skills.

Thus, the overall findings mean that there is a weak relationship of self-awareness of the life skills among the profile of the BTTE students.

Table 14. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Decision-making

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.041	0.05	Weak Relationship
Sex	0.329	0.05	Moderate Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.339	0.05	Moderate Relationship
Total	0.236	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 14 shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.236) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of decision-making. It shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.041, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their decision-making skills. It indicates that the older respondents tend to have a higher decision-making. It appears that there is a moderate relationship (r-value = 0.329, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's sex and their decision-making skills. It pointed toward that the female respondents have a decision-making. It is contrast in the study of Harris, he stated that women and men do have distinct critical thinking and decision-making styles, it does not show a difference between critical thinking scores of men versus women.

Furthermore, in terms of area of specialization, it displays shows that there is a moderate relationship (r-value = 0.339, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's area of specialization and their decision-making skills. It points toward that the Automotive students have the higher decision-making.

Thus, the overall findings mean that there is a weak relationship of Decision-making of the life skills among the profile of the BTTE students.

Table 15. Relationship between the Respondents Profile to Life Skills in terms of Problem Solving

Profile Variables	r -value	Significance Level	Interpretation
Age	0.016	0.05	Weak Relationship
Sex	0.016	0.05	Weak Relationship
Area of Specialization	0.054	0.05	Weak Relationship
Total	0.029	0.05	Weak Relationship

Table 15 shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.029) significant at 0.05 between the profile of the respondents to life skills in terms of problem solving. It shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.016, $p < 0.05$) between the respondents age and their problem-solving skills. It appears that there is a weak relationship (r-value = -0.016, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's sex and their problem-solving skills. It points toward that the female respondents have a higher problem solving.

Additionally, in terms of area of specialization, it displays shows that there is a weak relationship (r-value = 0.054, $p < 0.05$) between the respondent's area of specialization and their problem-solving skills

Thus, the overall findings mean that there is a weak relationship of problem solving of the life skills among the profile of the BTTE students.

Table 16. Regression of Life Skills in terms of Critical Thinking on the Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Beta	P-value	Sig. Level
Active Engagement	0.065	-0.564	.000
Transfer of Knowledge	0.454	0.020	.000
Deliberate Practice	0.072	-0.509	.000
Self-reflection	0.726	0.120	.000

Table 16 displays the regression analysis between learning through simulation and life skills of BTTE students in terms of critical thinking. As shown in the table, every standard deviation increases in the active engagement there is 0.065, transfer of knowledge there is 0.454, deliberate practice there is 0.072 and self-reflection there is 0.726 with a (p-value = -0.564) active engagement, (p-value = 0.020) transfer of knowledge, (p-value = -0.509) deliberate practice, and (p-value = 0.120) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

Likewise, the adjusted R square of 0.509 shows that the active engagement and transfer of knowledge that entered in the equation account for 50.9 % of any variance on the learning through simulation of the BTTE students in enhancing their life skills with F-value of 7.50 which is significant .000 level.

The results indicate that the students who are actively engaged on hands on activities and can transfer knowledge are students who encourage them to develop a deeper understanding of content by working with and can apply their new knowledge to new situations are those students who can enhance their Life Skills in terms of Critical Thinking.

Furthermore, the finding of this study is consistent with the study of Asaro (2010), who stated that it is one of the most common strategies in promoting active learning. It helps to motivate students toward learning through application of the information within a new setting, it develops critical thinking skills.

Table 17. Regression of Life Skills in terms of Self-awareness on the Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Beta	P-value	Sig. Level
Active Engagement	0.385	0.149	.000
Transfer of Knowledge	-0.294	0.112	.000
Deliberate Practice	0.022	0.926	.000
Self-reflection	0.884	0.002	.000

Table 17 displays the regression analysis between learning through simulation and life skills of BTTE students in terms of self-awareness.

The table reveals, every standard deviation increases in the active engagement there is 0.385, transfer of knowledge there is -0.294, deliberate practice there is 0.022 and self-reflection there is 0.884 with a (p-value = 0.149) active engagement, (p-value = 0.112) transfer of knowledge, (p-value = -0.926) deliberate practice, and (p-value = 0.002) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

Moreover, the adjusted R square of 0.540 shows that the deliberate practice and self-reflection that entered in the equation account for 54 % of any variance on the learning through simulation of the BTTE students in enhancing their life skills with F-value of 4 which is significant at.000 level.

The results indicate that the students who engaged themselves in deliberate practices on hands on activities and have self-reflection are students who improve their performance over time in their goal and motivation and question oneself in a positive way are those students who can enhance their Life Skills in terms of Self-awareness.

Table 18. Regression of Life Skills in terms of Decision-making on the Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Beta	P-value	Sig. Level
Active Engagement	-0.240	0.442	.000
Transfer of Knowledge	0.101	0.636	.000
Deliberate Practice	0.597	0.047	.000
Self-reflection	0.589	0.058	.000

The table shows that, every standard deviation increases in the active engagement there is -0.240, transfer of knowledge there is 0.101, deliberate practice there is 0.597 and self-reflection there is 0.589 with a (p-value = 0.442) active engagement, (p-value = 0.636) transfer of knowledge, (p-value = -0.047) deliberate practice, and (p-value = 0.058) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

Moreover, the adjusted R square of 0.366 shows that the transfer of knowledge that entered in the equation account for 36.6 % of any variance on the learning through simulation of the BTTE students in enhancing their life skills with F-value of 4.61 which is significant at .000 level.

The results indicate that the students can transfer knowledge on hands activities that seeks to organize, create, capture or distribute knowledge are those students who can enhance their Life Skills in terms of decision-making.

Table 19. Regression of Life Skills in terms of Problem Solving on the Independent Variables

Independent Variable	Beta	P-value	Sig. Level
Active Engagement	0.219	0.572	.000
Transfer of Knowledge	0.549	0.050	.000
Deliberate Practice	-0.433	0.234	.000
Self-reflection	0.774	0.047	.000

Table 19 displays the regression analysis between learning through simulation and life skills of BTTE students in terms of problem solving.

The beta coefficients of 0.219 with a p-value = 0.572 (active engagement), 0.549 with a p-value = 0.050 (transfer of knowledge), -0.433 with a p-value = 0.234 (deliberate practice) and 0.774 with a p-value = 0.047 (self-reflection) were found significant at .000 level respectively.

Moreover, the adjusted R square of 0.399 shows that the deliberate practice and self-reflection that entered in the equation account for 39.9 % of any variance on the learning through simulation of the BTTE students in enhancing their life skills with F-value of 5.16 which is significant at .000 level.

The results indicate that the students can transfer knowledge on hands activities and engage themselves in deliberate practice are students who ensure the availability of the output to the future users and have aim at improving performance, intentional, designed for the current skill level, combined with immediate feedback and repetitions are those students who can enhance their Life Skills in terms of Problem Solving.

DISCUSSION

This section summarizes and illustrates the results that the researchers have gathered from the study.

1. Profile of the Respondents

The majority of the respondents are in the age of 22 years old with a frequency of 12(48%) are male (18 or 69%) and (10 or 38%) are Automotive Engineering Technology (AET) students.

2. Learning through Simulation

The respondents describe their learning through simulation as strongly agree ($\bar{X} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.48$) in terms of active engagement, strongly agree ($\bar{X} = 4.57$, $SD = 0.49$) in terms of transfer of knowledge, strongly agree ($\bar{X} = 4.67$, $SD = 0.49$) in terms of deliberate practice and strongly agree ($\bar{X} = 4.64$, $SD = 0.46$) in terms of self-reflection.

This finding is supported by Parson and Taylor (2018), they said that the concept of “student engagement” is predicted on the belief that learning improves when students are inquisitive, interested, or inspired and that learning tends to suffer when students are bored, dispassionate, disaffected or otherwise disengaged.

Furthermore, a study by Steinwart and Ziegler (2014), He argues that knowledge transfer is the practical problem of transferring knowledge from one part of the organization to another. It seeks to organize, create, capture, or distribute knowledge and ensure its availability for future users.

Moreover, according to the study of McGaghie (2015), he argues that deliberate practice is a highly structured actively engaged in with the specific goal of improving performance. Engaging in deliberate practice, the improvement of your performance over time is the goal and motivation. Deliberate practice means repetition. It means performing the task with the aim of increasing your mastery of one or more aspects of the task.

Lastly, according to the study of Odayte (2017), she stated that student’s academic success requires not only action, but also reflection-that is, reflecting on what they have done, what they are doing and what they will do.

3. Life Skills

The respondents describe their life skills as agree ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.52$) in terms critical thinking, agree ($\bar{X} = 4.49$, $SD = 0.53$) in terms of self-awareness, strongly agree ($\bar{X} = 4.55$, $SD = 0.54$) in terms of decision-making, agree ($\bar{X} = 4.50$, $SD = 0.52$) and agree ($\bar{X} = 4.26$, $SD = 0.65$) in terms of problem solving.

4. Relationship of Respondents Profile to Life Skills

The relationship of the respondent’s profile to their life skills displays weak relationship as the data result tabulated. This finding is supported to the study of

Özdemir (2019), Kürüm (2015), Çekiç (2018), Akar (2017) also viewed the factors affecting critical thinking skills and the result of these studies teacher candidates critical thinking skill scores were not significantly different between the gender variable. When gender and critical thinking sub-skills scores were compared, there was significant difference between gender and assumption identification.

5. Regression Analysis of Life Skills of the Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education students on the Independent Variables

Critical Thinking, active engagement, transfer of knowledge, deliberate practice and self-reflection significantly enhances the life skills of the respondents with beta coefficients of 0.065 with a (p-value = -0.564) active engagement, 0.454 with a (p-value = 0.020) transfer of knowledge, 0.072 with a (p-value = -0.509) deliberate practice and 0.726 with a (p-value = 0.120) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

Furthermore, the finding of this study is consistent with the study of Asaro (2010), who stated that it is one of the most common strategies in promoting active learning. It helps to motivate students toward learning through application of the information within a new setting, it develops critical thinking skills.

The above finding is supported by Kahu (2018), stated that research has demonstrated that engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus, motivates them to practice higher level critical thinking skills and promotes meaningful learning experience. Instructors who adopt a student approach to instruction increase opportunities for student engagement, which then helps everyone more successfully achieve the courses learning objective.

Self-awareness, active engagement, transfer of knowledge, deliberate practice and self-reflection significantly enhances the life skills of the respondents with beta coefficients of 0.385 with a (p-value = 0.149) active engagement, -0.294 with a (p-value = 0.112) transfer of knowledge, 0.022 with a (p-value = -0.926) deliberate practice and 0.884 with a (p-value = 0.002) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

The findings of this study are consistent with the study Hatton & Smith (1995), they stated that self-reflection is questioning oneself in a positive way and the deciding whether there is a better or more efficient way of doing it in the future. They identified four essential issues concerning reflection: we should learn to frame and reframe complex or ambiguous problems, test out various interpretations and then modify our actions consequently.

Decision-making, active engagement, transfer of knowledge, deliberate practice and self-reflection significantly enhances the life skills of the respondents with beta coefficients of -0.240 with a (p-value = 0.442) active engagement, 0.101 with a (p-value = 0.636) transfer of knowledge, 0.597 (p-value = -0.047) deliberate practice and 0.589 with a (p-value = 0.058) self-reflection respectively both significant .000 level.

This supported the study of Yesilbas and Lossent (2015), they argue that knowledge sharing leads to improve decision-making. Knowledge has important role in individual Decision-making. To have a good decision-making knowledge has to be shared.

Problem Solving, active engagement, transfer of knowledge, deliberate practice and self-reflection significantly enhances the life skills of the respondents with beta coefficients of 0.219 with a p-value = 0.572 (active engagement), 0.549 with a p-value = 0.050 (transfer of knowledge), -0.433 with a p-value = 0.234 (deliberate practice) and 0.774 with a p-value = 0.047 (self-reflection) were found significant at .000 level respectively.

The above findings are supported to the study of Goodarzi, et.al (2018), he argues that transfer of knowledge is very much related to the problem of knowledge integration, knowledge application and knowledge use in the “real world”. Knowledge transfer is not about producing information resources at the end of a project or making those resources available to used. Rather it is about reducing the gap between what is known and what is used. Knowledge transfer should be considered at the start of project by identifying who will use the projects, result and planning to obtain results that fits user`s needs and experiences.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing summary of findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Most of the respondents are in the age of 22 years old, Male and Automotive Engineering Technology students.
2. Learning through simulation of the 2nd year (LDP) Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education-BTTE students illustrate as strongly agree.
3. The life skills of the 2nd year (LDP) Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education students illustrate as agree.
4. There is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents in enhancing the life skills of the 2nd year (LDP) Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education students.
5. The learning through simulation significantly enhances the life skills of the 2nd year (LDP) Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education students if they engage themselves on hands on activities, motivate to perform task, apply new knowledge to create a product and accept feedback from others to improve performance the students can enhance their life skills.

Recommendations

As stated in the limitations and capabilities, there are few recommendations for the improvement of this research.

1. For future researchers, that will conduct a study related to this paper, it is highly recommend conducting a physical survey to extract more reliable data that may give you accurate results and to expand their topics.
2. It is recommended to use a test of significance to calculate the p-value in the correlation analysis, for the reason that the correlation analysis provide only the r-value which only tells us the strength and direction of relationship.

3. To have a reliable data result, it is also recommended to expand the research locale, for which the population may increase and to give a better a result.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that all research protocols involving ethics in research were complied with for the protection of all people and institutions involved in the conduct of the study.

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